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2 **Sanitation of olive plants infected by *Verticillium dahliae* using heat**
3 **treatments**

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13 **Short title:** Heat treatments to remove *Verticillium dahliae* from olive

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2 **Abstract**

3 Verticillium wilt, which is caused by the fungus *Verticillium dahliae*, is currently the
4 most important disease affecting olive in the Mediterranean Basin. There are no
5 effective treatments for controlling this disease. The use of infected nursery stocks has
6 largely contributed to the spread of the pathogen, therefore, the development of
7 treatments to preventively sanitise the propagation stock is critical in the nursery
8 industry. Here, we describe novel techniques to achieve this aim. We evaluated the
9 effects of several temperature-exposure time combinations: i) the survival of pathogen
10 on culture medium (PDA); ii) the pathogen viability on infected shoots and plants; iii)
11 the vegetative growth of plants of several cultivars; and iv) the rooting ability of
12 cuttings. The colonies of the pathogen growing in PDA were killed after 8 h and 60 min
13 of exposure at 40 and 47°C, respectively. Temperatures $\geq 42^\circ\text{C}$ for at least 2 h were
14 lethal for the pathogen infecting the shoots. Likewise, moist hot air treatments at 42-
15 44°C for 6-12 h eradicated the pathogen, without compromising the viability of the
16 plants. Five olive cultivars were also evaluated and classified according to their
17 thermotolerance as follows: sensitive ('Chiquitita'), moderately sensitive ('Koroneiki',
18 'Frantoio', and 'Picual') and heat tolerant ('Arbequina'). However, the optimised
19 sanitation methods were applicable to all of the cultivars. Finally, heat treatments
20 were applied to unrooted cuttings, which severely affected their rooting ability. In
21 summary, we developed a hot air treatment to produce *V. dahliae*-free olive nursery
22 plants.

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2 INTRODUCTION

3 Verticillium wilt caused by the fungus *Verticillium dahliae* Kleb., is a major disease of
4 olive (*Olea europaea* L.), mainly affecting new plantations (López-Escudero & Mercado-
5 Blanco, 2011; Jiménez-Díaz *et al.*, 2012). Several factors make this disease difficult to
6 control, such as (i) the extreme susceptibility of most of the dominant olive cultivars,
7 with the number of moderately resistant cultivars being very restricted (López-
8 Escudero & Mercado-Blanco, 2011); (ii) the capacity of *V. dahliae* to survive in the soil
9 for up to 15 years (Wilhelm, 1955); (iii) the ability of this pathogen to infect a wide host
10 range and spre (Thanassoulopoulos *et al.*,
11 1981; Jiménez-Díaz *et al.*, 2012), and (iv) the limited effectiveness of chemical
12 treatments because *V. dahliae* inoculum survives in the soil as dormant microsclerotia
13 and infects the vasculature of plants, where it is difficult to reach with fungicides
14 (López-Escudero & Mercado-Blanco, 2011; Jiménez-Díaz *et al.*, 2012).

15 Several changes in agronomic practices that have occurred over the last few
16 decades might have contributed to the increased severity of the disease. First, new
17 olive orchards have been established in soils that were already infested by *V. dahliae*
18 because they were previously cropped with susceptible species, such as cotton
19 (Rodríguez *et al.* 2011). Second, bare-soil management by herbicide applications,
20 which have become very popular for preventing competition from other plants for the
21 use of available water, concomitantly eliminates adventitious vegetation, such as
22 species of the Brassicaceae family that show an elevated bio-fumigation capacity
23 (Bejarano-Alcázar, 2008). Third, pruning remnants were traditionally burned but more
24 recently are mulched onto the ground, spreading the pathogen across the orchard, and

1 finally, some modern olive plantations are frequently irrigated with infested water
2 (García-Cabello *et al.*, 2012).

3 The propagation of infested olive stocks by commercial nurseries might have
4 also contributed to the spread of Verticillium wilt (Thanassouloupoulos *et al.*, 1980;
5 Nigro *et al.*, 2005). Olive is clonally propagated (Barranco *et al.*, 2010), and
6 consequently, most of semi-hardwood cuttings coming from an infected mother plant
7 are also infected. For instance, Thanassouloupoulos (1993) detected *V. dahliae* on
8 asymptomatic three-year-old plants in four out of the nine nurseries that were
9 examined in an affected area of Greece in 1991. In Italy, Nigro *et al.* (2005) detected
10 the pathogen in 50% of the olive nurseries in the Apulia region, which may explain the
11 presence of Verticillium wilt in plantations that are established on pathogen-free soils.
12 In the Andalusia region (southern Spain), which is the main olive-producing area
13 worldwide, 15% of symptomless self-propagated plants in registered olive nurseries
14 were infected with *V. dahliae* in surveys that were conducted in 2006-2007 (Jiménez-
15 Díaz *et al.*, 2012; J. Anda, *personal communication*). Thus, the sanitary control of the
16 olive cuttings, and especially the mother plants, is a crucial step for the olive nursery
17 industry.

18 Testing for *V. dahliae* in nurseries are generally based on visual tests with a
19 subpopulation tested by molecular methods. Infected cuttings might escape these
20 surveys and contribute to pathogen spread. Consequently, techniques and strategies
21 to effectively screen the olive mother plants and their cuttings and ultimately
22 eradicate the pathogen from those already infected are required by the nursery
23 industry. Germplasm banks, which in the case of perennial crops adopt the form of
24 living collections, also demand these techniques due to two main reasons; first, any

1 new accession should be tested and found to be *V. dahliae*-free prior its introduction
2 into the collection (Caballero & Del Río, 2005), and second, germplasm banks should
3 be able to sanitise infected plants given the fact that these banks cannot afford to lose
4 the unique genetic diversity that they conserve.

5 This study aimed to contribute to Verticillium wilt management for both the
6 nursery industry and germplasm banks. To do so, we followed previous research in
7 several perennial crops, such as citrus (*Citrus* species) (Hoffman *et al.*, 2013), grape
8 (*Vitis vinifera* L.) (Waite & Morton, 2007), and pecan (*Carya illinoensis* (Wangenh.) K.
9 Koch) (Sanderlin & Melanson, 2008), in which treatments based on the application of
10 dry heat or hot water (thereafter heat treatments) were able to reduce or eliminate
11 different pathogens from the plant tissues. The effectiveness of the heat treatments is
12 based on the fact that dormant plant organs can withstand high temperatures (Agrios,
13 2005). Despite olive being an evergreen species without dormant organs, we applied
14 heat treatments to control *V. dahliae*, taking advantage the thermosensitivity of this
15 pathogen (Tjamos & Fravel, 1995). For instance, temperatures of approximately 35-
16 37°C for 3-4 weeks are lethal for *V. dahliae* microsclerotia, which are the most
17 thermotolerant structures of this pathogen (Subbarao & Hubbard, 1996). In addition,
18 microsclerotia only appear in dead or dying plant tissues (López-Escudero & Mercado-
19 Blanco, 2011), which are absent in healthy or symptomless olive plants sold by the
20 nursery industry. Evidence that heat treatment can control Verticillium wilt of olive
21 was documented in Syria, where the pathogen was eliminated from trees that were
22 covered with a portable-plastic greenhouse for 15-20 days during the summer (Al-
23 Hamad, 1993).

1 In order to optimise the use of heat treatments as a procedure for eliminating
2 *V. dahliae* from infected olive plants, we defined the ranges of temperature and
3 exposure time that are necessary to kill the pathogen with no damage to the plant. To
4 do so, we determined the effect of temperature-exposure time combinations as
5 follows: (i) the survival of *V. dahliae* on pure culture medium; (ii) the pathogen viability
6 in infected shoots and young plants; (iii) the vegetative growth of different heat-
7 treated olive cultivars; and (iv) the rooting ability of semi-hardwood cuttings.

8

9 **MATERIALS AND METHODS**

10 **Effect of heat treatments on the mycelial growth (*Experiments 1-2*)**

11 Colonies of *V. dahliae* were subjected to heat treatment to determine the minimum
12 exposure times that are required to substantially reduce the pathogen viability at given
13 temperatures. Five *V. dahliae* isolates were grown for approximately 4 days on potato-
14 dextrose agar (PDA; Difco Laboratories, Detroit, MI, USA) at room temperature
15 (approximately 20°C). Because the olive isolates of *V. dahliae* can be classified into
16 defoliating (D) and non-defoliating (ND) pathotypes according to their ability to cause
17 the complete fall of green leaves (López-Escudero & Mercado-Blanco, 2011; Jiménez-
18 Díaz *et al.*, 2012), we selected three D isolates (V-117 I, V-138 I, and V-937 I) and two
19 ND isolates (V-249 I and V-789 I) from the Andalusia region, Spain. The three D isolates
20 belong to the same Vegetative Compatibility Group (VCG1A), and the ND isolates V-
21 249 I and V-789 I belong to the groups VCG2A and VCG4B, respectively (Collado-
22 Romero *et al.*, 2006). All of the isolates were characterised and kindly supplied by Dr. J.
23 Mercado-Blanco from CSIC-IAS, Córdoba, Spain. Mycelial plugs (8 mm in diameter)
24 were taken from the edge of 3-day-old colonies of each *V. dahliae* isolate that was

1 grown on PDA medium and transferred to Petri dishes with the same medium. The
2 dishes were sealed with Parafilm and placed in closed plastic containers at $20 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ for
3 2 days in the dark. The sizes of the colonies were then marked in the dishes that were
4 placed in darkened growth chambers at the different heat treatments. Finally, the
5 colony growth of each Petri dish was measured in two perpendicular directions, and
6 the growth was expressed as millimetres per day. The temperature was monitored
7 continuously with mercury-filled thermometers.

8 In *Experiment 1*, two D isolates (V-138 I and V-937 I) and two ND isolates (V-249
9 I and V-789 I) were heat-treated at 45, 47, 50, and 55°C for 15, 30, 45, and 60 min. In
10 *Experiment 2*, two D isolates (V-117 I and V-138 I) and two ND isolates (V-249 I and V-
11 789 I) were heat-treated at 40, 42, 44, and 46°C for 1, 2, 4, 8, and 24 h. The
12 experiments consisted of five dishes replications for each isolate and temperature-
13 exposure time combination. Both experiments were conducted twice.

14 Mycelial growth (mm day^{-1}) and exposure time (min or h) were treated as a
15 continuous variables, while the *V. dahliae* isolates were treated as class variables.
16 Multiple linear regressions were used to identify the variables and interactions that are
17 associated with the final mycelial growth. Multiple linear regressions were performed
18 considering the significances of each parameter and the whole regression, the
19 coefficient of determination (R^2) and the coefficient of determination adjusted for
20 degrees of freedom (R_a^2). Finally, the influence of the *V. dahliae* isolate on the
21 required exposure time to cause pathogen death was measured using viability curves
22 as estimated by the Kaplan–Meier method in which the pathogen viability (1 = alive or
23 0 = killed pathogen by hot temperature) and exposure time were used as the event
24 and time variables, respectively. Moreover, the Kaplan–Meier percentiles (50 and 90%)

1 were calculated. The effect of the *V. dahliae* isolate on the required exposure time to
2 cause pathogen death was studied using a Long rank test at $P = 0.05$. The statistical
3 analyses were conducted using Statistix 10 (Analytical Software, Tallahassee, FL).

4 **Effect of hot water treatments on the pathogen viability in the shoots (*Experiments 3***
5 **and 4)**

6 The following experiments were designed exclusively to test the effect of Hot Water
7 Treatments (HWTs) on *V. dahliae* in the xylem vessels of olive shoots. For this, we used
8 naturally infected shoots that were collected from a commercial olive orchard that was
9 located in Sevilla province, Andalusia region. We selected shoots (~ 5 mm in diameter
10 × 150 mm long) with five to six internodes with three or four pairs of leaves. The
11 shoots were cut from olive trees cv. Picual with unequivocal Verticillium wilt
12 symptoms, bagged in plastic and transported at 10°C immediately to the laboratory.
13 Before the HWTs, the shoots were labelled and cut into two pieces. The basal end (~
14 50 mm long) of each shoot was used to evaluate the HWTs effect, while the rest of the
15 shoot was used to confirm that the shoot was infected by *V. dahliae*. For the latter, we
16 cut with a sterile scalpel samples of vascular tissue (3 to 4 × 3 × 1 to 2 mm) and placed
17 the samples in Petri dishes containing acidified PDA (2.5 ml of 25% [Vol/Vol] lactic acid
18 per litre of medium) to minimise bacterial growth. The Petri dishes were incubated at
19 $23 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ in the dark until the *V. dahliae* colonies were large enough to be examined. In
20 addition, ten of these isolates were characterised for their pathotype by duplex,
21 nested PCR analysis as described by Mercado-Blanco *et al.* 2003a. We rejected for this
22 and subsequent experiments those shoots from which the pathogen was not isolated
23 before the heat treatments.

1 In *Experiment 3*, the shoots were immersed in water baths at 45 and 60°C for 1
2 h. In *Experiment 4*, the shoots were immersed in water baths at 40, 42, 44, and 46°C
3 for 1, 2, 4, 8, and 24 h.

4 Ten shoots were used for each temperature-exposure time combination, and
5 the experiments were replicated twice. The data of both replicates were combined
6 because the differences between them were not significant (Chi-square test; $P < 0.05$).
7 In *Experiment 4*, those treatments that were not able to eradicate the pathogen from
8 the shoots were compared using Zar's test of multiple comparisons of proportions
9 (Zar, 2010).

10 To confirm the pathogen viability after HWTs, the treated tissues were planted
11 onto acidified PDA. In addition, real-time PCR with the specific primers VertBt-F and
12 VertBt-R (Atallah *et al.*, 2007) was run to confirm the presence of pathogen DNA
13 according to Imperato, 2010. For this analysis, pieces (~ 3-4 g) of shoots with leaves
14 were placed in plastic bags (BP-MG model; Plant Print Diagnostics, Valencia, Spain)
15 with 5 ml of PBS at pH 7, and the tissue was crushed using a rubber hammer. DNA was
16 isolated using the DNeasy Plant Mini Kit (Qiagen, Hilden, Germany). The PCR reactions
17 (final volume 20 µl) consisted of 0.6 µl of each primer (10 µM), 10 µl of Power SYBR
18 Green PCR Master Mix (Applied Biosystems) and 4 µl of target DNA (30 ng) that was
19 diluted five times. The real-time PCR was carried out under generic cycling conditions
20 (95°C for 10 min, 45 cycles of 95°C for 15 s and 60°C for 1 min) followed by a
21 dissociation step consisting of 95°C for 5 s, 60°C for 1 min and 97°C for 15 s. The real-
22 time PCR was performed using an iCycler (Bio-Rad, Hercules, CA, USA), and the results
23 were analysed with the manufacturer's software IQTM-5 (Optical System Software v
24 5.0a). After each run, the melting curves were analysed to check for the presence of

1 non-specific amplification. Negative controls containing olive DNA were included in
2 every run. This qPCR protocol was applied in all of the experiments that were carried
3 out in this study.

4 **Effect of moist hot air treatments on infected young plants (*Experiments 5-7*)**

5 The following experiments were conducted using one-year-old plants that were
6 infected with *V. dahliae* and that were subjected to different moist hot air treatments
7 (HATs). Olive plants of cvs. Picual and Frantoio, which are susceptible and moderately
8 resistant to the pathogen, respectively (López-Escudero & Mercado-Blanco, 2011),
9 were propagated by semi-hardwood cuttings using indole-3-butyric acid (IBA)
10 potassium salt (Barranco *et al.*, 2010). Once the cuttings rooted, they were
11 transplanted into sterilised plastic pots (15 × 15 × 20 cm) with sterilised soil (sand:
12 loam, 2:1, v/v) and grown at 19-30°C in a closed greenhouse for one year. At this time,
13 the plants were root-dip inoculated for 20 min in a suspension of 10⁷ conidia ml⁻¹ of
14 the V-138 isolate of *V. dahliae* as previously described (Mercado-Blanco *et al.*, 2003b).
15 Inoculated and non-inoculated plants (immersed in water) were then transplanted to
16 sterilised soil. The plants were fertilised once (7 g of P₂O₅ + 2 g of NO₃K + 1 g of CO₃Ca
17 + 1 g of SO₄Mg + 0.6 g of CO₃Mg per plant) and irrigated as needed. qPCR and
18 isolations to PDA were conducted to ascertain the presence of *V. dahliae* in the
19 inoculated and control plants before and after HATs. To apply HATs, the infected and
20 control plants were placed in closed 40-L plastic containers with 3 cm of water at the
21 base. Water was sprayed into the containers, which were incubated in darkened
22 growth chambers at different temperature-exposure time combinations according to
23 the following experiments: *Experiment 5*, plants of the susceptible cv. Picual were hot-
24 air-treated at 40°C for 12 h; 42, 44, and 46°C for 6 and 12 h 30 days after inoculation

1 when they began to show *Verticillium* wilt symptoms; *Experiment 6*, symptomless
2 plants of the cv. Picual were hot-air-treated at 40°C for 12 h; 42, 44, and 46°C for 6 and
3 12 h 10 days after inoculation when they were colonised by the pathogen as verified
4 by qPCR; and *Experiment 7*. Symptomless plants of the resistant cv. Frantoio were hot-
5 air-treated at 40, 42, 44, and 46°C for 6 and 12 h 170 days after inoculation when they
6 were colonised by the pathogen as verified by qPCR.

7 We evaluated plant survival and the presence of *V. dahliae* in the vascular
8 system of plants by isolation on PDA and qPCR 7 days after HATs. In addition, plants
9 were periodically checked for *V. dahliae* symptoms for eight months after inoculation.

10 Each experiment consisted of three inoculated and three non-inoculated plants
11 for each temperature-exposure time combination, and the experiments were repeated
12 twice. Because there were no clear differences between the HATs and experiments,
13 we just compared the survival percentage the heat-air-treated plants with the survival
14 percentage of the control plants using a Chi-square test.

15 **Effect of moist hot air treatments on the survival and vegetative growth of different**
16 **cultivars (*Experiment 8*)**

17 Because in the previous section, the non-inoculated plants of cv. Frantoio were
18 more tolerant to HATs than were the non-inoculated plants cv. Picual, *Experiment 8*
19 was conducted to test the effect of HATs on the vegetative growth and survival of one-
20 year-old healthy plants of five cultivars: Arbequina, Frantoio, Koroneiki, Picual, and
21 Chiquitita. The HATs were conducted as described previously.

22 The temperature-exposure time combinations that were evaluated were: 40,
23 44, 46, and 48°C for 3, 6, 12, and 24 h. After the HATs, the plants were grown at 19-
24 30°C in a closed greenhouse where the lateral shoots were periodically removed. Plant

1 survival and growth of the main shoot (mm) were recorded once every two-weeks for
2 2 months. The weight of vegetative growth (g) of each plant was recorded at the end
3 of the experiment. The experiment consisted of three replicates (plants) per cultivar
4 and temperature-exposure time combination, and the experiment was conducted
5 twice.

6 The effect of the temperature (T_e), exposure time (T_i), and cultivar (C_v) on the
7 survival of the treated plants was studied using a logistic regression expressed as
8 follows:

$$9 \quad \text{Logit}(Y) = aT_e + bT_i + cC_v + K$$

10 where Y is the incidence of plant death; K is a constant of regression; and a , b ,
11 and c are the fitted parameters of the regression. A stepwise regression was used to
12 determine the statistical significance of each independent variable. At each step in the
13 process, the candidate variable was selected according to the likelihood ratio statistic,
14 i.e., when the difference of the deviances of the models, including and excluding the
15 candidate variable ($Df_n - Df_{n-1}$), were significant according to the Chi-square test
16 (Collett, 2003). To determine the differences in tolerance to HATs among the olive
17 cultivars, an analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed using Arcsin-transformed
18 data on the percentage of plant survival. The cultivar means were compared using
19 Tukey's honestly significant difference (HSD) test at $P = 0.05$.

20 To determine the effect of HATs on the weight of vegetative growth (g) of the
21 the treated plants, we calculated the percentage of inhibition of growth in relation to
22 the non-treated plants [I (%)]. The relationship between I (%) and exposure time [T_i
23 (h)] accurately fitted ($P < 0.05$; $R^2 > 0.860$) to a line for each temperature and cultivar
24 expressed as follows:

1 $I (\%) = \alpha \times T_i (h)$

2 where the parameter α represents the percentage of inhibition of weight growth per
3 hour of exposure at a given temperature and cultivar. Similarly, a linear regression
4 analysis was used to evaluate relationships between the percentage of inhibition of
5 weight growth per hour of exposure time, i.e., the parameter α , and temperature for
6 each cultivar according to the following equation:

7 $\alpha (\%/h) = \beta \times T_i (^\circ C) + \delta$

8 where parameter β represents the percentage of inhibition of weight growth per hour
9 of exposure in Celsius degrees, and δ is the elevation of the line being both parameters
10 characteristic of each cultivar for $T^a \geq 40^\circ C$. In this way, the tolerance of each cultivar
11 to temperature is only expressed by the parameters β and δ . Finally, comparisons of
12 regression lines of the cultivars were made considering the homogeneity of variances,
13 slopes (β), and elevations (δ).

14 **Effect of hot water treatments on the rooting ability of the cuttings (*Experiments 9***
15 **and *10*)**

16 The last experiments were designed to test the effect of HWT on the rooting ability of
17 semi-hardwood cuttings because olive is propagated by these kind of propagules that
18 are obtained from mother plants (Barranco *et al.*, 2010). Cuttings were collected from
19 healthy potted olive plants cv. Picual as described in above section for the shoots.

20 In *Experiment 9*, the cuttings were immersed in water baths at 45, 50, 55, and
21 60°C for 30 and 60 min. In *Experiment 10*, the cuttings were immersed in water baths
22 at 40, 42, and 44°C for 1, 2, and 4 h.

23 The heat-water-treated and non-treated (control) cuttings were then subjected
24 to conventional rooting using IBA (Barranco *et al.*, 2010). The cuttings were tested for

1 survival and rooting capacity at 15, 30, and 60 days after the HWTs. Both experiments
2 consisted of 25 replicates (cuttings) and were conducted twice. Because there were no
3 significant (Chi-square test; $P > 0.05$) differences between the repetitions of each
4 experiment, the data were combined, and the Chi-square test was used to study the
5 effect of HWTs on the percentage rooting ability of olive cuttings.

6 RESULTS

7 Effect of heat treatments on mycelial growth (*Experiments 1 and 2*)

8 The effect of temperature and exposure time on mycelial growth of *V. dahliae* isolates
9 is shown in Figures 1 and 2. In *Experiment 1*, pathogen colonies on PDA that were
10 exposed to 55 and 47°C were killed after 45 and 60 min of exposure, respectively. The
11 temperature and exposure time significantly affected (Lineal Regression Analysis; $P <$
12 0.001) the mycelial growth of the pathogen. In contrast, the *V. dahliae* isolate,
13 pathotype, and different interactions did not have a significant ($P > 0.05$) effect on
14 mycelial growth except in the treatment of 60 min at 45°C in which V138 I and V 937 I
15 showed growth while the remaining isolates did not (Fig. 1). The data gave a good fit (P
16 < 0.001 , $R^2 = 0.783$ and $R^2_a = 0.781$) for the model [Y (*mm/day*) = $6.36 - 0.08 \times$
17 *Temperature* (°C) $- 0.04 \times$ *Time* (*min*)]. When we used mortality as dependent variable
18 (Kaplan-Meier analysis), there was no significant ($P > 0.05$) difference among the
19 isolates. For example, exposure times between 57-59 min at temperatures $\geq 47^\circ\text{C}$ were
20 enough to cause a 90% of mortality for all of the isolates. In this case, the ND isolates
21 were more tolerant of 45°C than D isolates (Table 1).

22 When lower temperatures and longer exposure times were applied (*Experiment*
23 *2*), the temperature, the isolate, and their interaction significantly ($P < 0.003$) affected
24 mycelial growth. In contrast, the pathotype and isolate did not have a significant ($P >$

1 0.05) effect on mycelial growth. The multiple linear regression model that was fit to
2 the data showed $P < 0.001$, $R^2 = 0.530$, and $R^2_a = 0.511$. In this case, all of the pathogen
3 colonies that were exposed to temperatures $\geq 42^\circ\text{C}$ for 8 h were killed (Fig. 2). The
4 isolates V-789 I and V-249 I were slightly more thermotolerant than were the other
5 two isolates according to the Kaplan–Meier percentiles (Table 1). For example, the
6 time to reach 50 and 90% of mortality of the V-789 I colonies incubated at 44°C was 8
7 and 20.8 h, respectively, while it was 6 and 19.2 h for the remaining isolates. None of
8 tested isolates developed microsclerotia in the culture medium during the
9 experiments.

10 **Effect of hot water treatments on the pathogen in infected shoots (*Experiments 3*** 11 **and 4)**

12 The immersion of infected shoots in water at 45 or 60°C for 1 h severely affected the
13 pathogen viability. The fungus was only isolated from four cuttings (20%) that were
14 treated at 45°C for 1 h.

15 When the infected shoots were subjected to temperatures from 40 to 46°C for
16 1 to 24 h (*Experiment 4*), the temperatures 44 and 46°C were lethal for the pathogen
17 for all of the studied exposure times. At lower temperatures, the impact of treatment
18 also depended on the exposure time. For instance, the pathogen was isolated from
19 40% of the shoots that were treated at 42°C for 1 h but not from the shoots that were
20 exposed longer. Moreover, *V. dahliae* was isolated at similar ($P > 0.05$) percentages
21 from shoots that were treated at 40°C for 1 h (100%) and 40°C for 2 h (90%). These last
22 treatments were significantly ($P < 0.05$) less effective at killing the pathogen than were
23 40°C for 4 h (40%) or 42°C for 1 h (40%).

1 The ten *V. dahliae* isolates were characterised as members of the D pathotype
2 by PCR.

3 **Effect of hot air treatments on infected young plants (*Experiments 5-7*)**

4 HATs severely affected the pathogen viability with subsequent successful isolations
5 from only two symptomatic plants of cv. Picual that had been treated at 40°C for 12 h
6 (*Experiment 5*). However, only three (6.2%) of these plants survived after HATs. In
7 contrast, 39 (81.2%) of the control plants survived the same treatments, these being
8 significantly (Chi-square Test; $P < 0.001$) more thermotolerant than the symptomatic
9 plants. For this reason, the following two experiments were carried out using
10 symptomless plants.

11 In *Experiment 6*, no pathogen was isolated from the symptomless plants of cv.
12 Picual after HATs. Overall, both the temperature and exposure time affected the
13 survival of the plants (Table 2). The HATs similarly affected (Chi-square Test, $P = 0.620$)
14 the control and symptomless plants, which showed 76 and 71% of survival
15 percentages, respectively. None of the heat-air-treated plants of cv. Picual showed wilt
16 symptoms during the following eight months. In contrast, all of the inoculated and
17 non-treated plants of cv. Picual showed disease symptoms and eventually died after
18 three months of inoculation (Fig. 3A).

19 In *Experiment 7*, all of the HATs killed *V. dahliae*, infecting the symptomless
20 plants of cv. Frantoio. Once again, the temperature and exposure time affected the
21 plant survival. The HATs significantly affected (Chi-square Test, $P < 0.001$) the survival
22 of infected plants (73%) compared to uninfected plants (100%; Table 2). In addition,
23 none of the heat-air-treated plants of cv. Frantoio showed disease symptoms during
24 the following eight months (Fig. 3B).

1 **Effect of hot air treatments on the survival and vegetative growth of different**
2 **cultivars (*Experiment 8*)**

3 The viability of the plants decreased while increasing the temperature and exposure
4 time. For example, none of the plants died when treated at 40 or 44°C for 3 h, while
5 the treatments at 52°C for 12 or 24 h killed all of the plants (Fig. 4). The multiple-
6 logistic regression showed that the temperature, exposure time, and cultivar
7 significantly affected (Extra Table 1; $P < 0.001$) plant survival. The plants of cvs.
8 Chiquitita and Picual were the most sensible plants (Tukey`s Test; $P < 0.05$). The latter
9 cultivar, however, did not show significant differences to the other evaluated cultivars
10 ('Arbequina', Koroneiki', and 'Frantoio').

11 The temperature and the exposure time affected the vegetative shoot growth
12 (mm) of the plants. Thus, as temperature and exposure time increased, the shoot
13 growth decreased and the survival of the plants was poorer. However, some of the
14 cultivars that were treated at lower temperatures (40-42°C) showed an increased
15 vegetative growth with respect to the non-treated plants. For example, the main shoot
16 of cv. Picual plants that were treated at 40°C for 24 h grew 78 mm more on average
17 than did the non-treated plants of the same cultivar (Extra Fig. 1).

18 The percentage of growth inhibition per hour of exposure as measured in
19 weight units increased linearly with the increasing of temperature from 40 to 52°C (Fig.
20 5). There were no significant ($P > 0.05$) differences between the regression line
21 elevations for the five cultivars. In contrast, significant ($P < 0.05$) differences were
22 found in their slopes, i.e., the percentage of inhibition of weight growth per hour of
23 exposure and Celsius degrees (β parameter) for each cultivar. Accordingly, cvs.
24 Chiquitita and Koroneiki plants were significantly ($P < 0.05$) more thermosensitive than

1 cvs. Picual and Arbequina plants. The plants of cv. Frantoio showed an intermediate
2 sensibility to HATs and showed no differences from the other groups.

3 **The effect of hot water treatments on the rooting of the cuttings (*Experiments 9 and***
4 ***10*)**

5 The HWTs severely affected the rooting ability of the cuttings. Thus, all of the
6 cuttings that were treated at temperatures from 50 to 60°C showed senescence
7 symptoms during the first week after the HWT, and none of them rooted (*Experiment*
8 *10*). When the cuttings were treated at 45°C, most of them died, and only two (4%),
9 which were treated for 30 min, rooted after six weeks. In contrast, 20 non-heat-
10 treated cuttings (40%) rooted during the experiment.

11 When we applied lower temperatures and longer exposure times, only the cuttings
12 that were treated at 40°C for 1, 2, and 4 h rooted during the 6 weeks after the HWTs,
13 showing a rooting percentage of 8, 16, and 36%, respectively. These rooting
14 percentages were significantly lower (Chi-square test; $P < 0.05$) than that observed in
15 the non-treated cuttings (48%).

16 **DISCUSSION**

17 The present study shows that simple treatments consisting of the application of
18 temperatures from 42 to 44°C for 6-12 h under moist conditions are able to eradicate
19 *V. dahliae* from infected one-year-old olive plants, enabling a healthy propagation
20 material. Because *V. dahliae* is frequently introduced in pathogen-free areas by
21 symptomless nursery stocks (Thanassouloupoulos *et al.*, 1980; Nigro *et al.*, 2005;
22 Rodríguez *et al.*, 2011) and no curative control measures are known (López-Escudero &
23 Mercado-Blanco, 2011; Jiménez-Díaz *et al.*, 2012), the preventive application of
24 sanitation measures to the propagation material is crucial to avoid the spread of the

1 pathogen. However, no effective sanitation measures have been developed for olive
2 plants. In contrast, the first culture-indexing procedure was used to eliminate
3 *Verticillium* from chrysanthemums during the 1940s. Similar methods were later
4 applied to other ornamental species, such as geraniums to eliminate *Xanthomonas*
5 *campestris* pv. *pelargonii* (Daughtrey & Benson, 2005). Likewise, in non-perennial
6 crops, such as mint (*Mentha spicata* L.) and artichoke (*Cynara scolymus* L.), the
7 micropropagation of shoots and HWTs has been developed to obtain *V. dahliae*-free
8 propagation material (Márquez *et al.*, 2000; Wang & Reed, 2003). The HWTs are
9 currently integrated into the standard nursery practice of grapevine (Waite & Morton,
10 2007).

11 Our results showed that *V. dahliae* colonies that were exposed to 40 and 47°C were
12 killed after 8 h and 60 min of exposure, respectively. Similarly, treatments consisting of
13 temperatures of 55, 50, 47, 45, 42, and 40°C for 15 min, 45 min, 2, 4, 24 and 24 h,
14 respectively, proved lethal for olive *V. dahliae* isolates from Syria (Al-Hamad *et al.*,
15 1997). Similar heat treatments (31-36°C for 10-14 h) have also been effective in
16 reducing the microsclerotia viability, the most thermotolerant structures of pathogen
17 (Tjamos & Fravel, 1995)

18 Interestingly, according to our results, the D or ND character of the *V. dahliae* isolates
19 affected their response to heat treatments. The D isolates showed greater
20 thermotolerance than did ND isolates when applying the treatment consisting of 45°C-
21 60 min. However, the opposite result was found when the isolates were subjected to
22 lower temperatures and longer exposure times, with the ND isolates being more
23 thermotolerant than the D isolates. This variation could be due to differential
24 thermotolerance among the population of pathogens as it was previously observed,

1 although further studies are necessary, including isolates from other olive-growing
2 areas (Bollen, 1985).

3 During the colonisation of the plant, *V. dahliae* grows upward through the
4 xylem vessels, producing mycelium and spores that spread through the aerial part of
5 the plant (Mercado-Blanco *et al.*, 2003a). In our study, the pathogen was eliminated
6 from previously colonised olive shoots after the immersion of the shoots in hot water
7 ($\geq 42^{\circ}\text{C}$) for at least 2 h. Therefore, temperatures from 40-44°C, which are easily
8 reached in Mediterranean areas during the summer, could be enough to kill the
9 pathogen in the aerial part of the olive, requiring new colonisation after the summer.
10 This result agrees with two main observations: (i) the Verticillium wilt epidemic in olive
11 fits a sigmoid-shaped curve, having the highest infection rate from winter to spring and
12 decreasing to minimum values during the summer (Navas-Cortés *et al.*, 2008), and (ii)
13 the pathogen detection by isolation on PDA or molecular techniques decreases
14 substantially during the summer (Morera *et al.*, 2005).

15 In the experiment that was conducted to sanitise inoculated one-year-old
16 plants, the symptomatic plants were more thermosensitive than were the
17 symptomless plants of the same cultivar. In line with this fact, we observed that the
18 olive trees showing *V. dahliae* symptoms are more sensible to frost than are their
19 healthy neighbours under field conditions. Based on the survival percentage and shoot
20 growth, the cultivars were classified into three categories: sensitive ('Chiquitita'),
21 moderately sensitive ('Koroneiki', 'Frantoio', and 'Picual') and heat tolerant
22 ('Arbequina'). Regardless the optimised treatments, which are able to eliminate the
23 pathogen from the plants (temperatures of 42-44°C for 6-12 h), were well tolerated for
24 all of the tested cultivars. In agreement with other perennial species, such as

1 grapevine, heat-treated young plants show a slower establishment process and suffer
2 delayed early growth. Nonetheless, this effect reduces over time and does not affect
3 the viability of the plantation (Waite & May, 2005; Gramaje *et al.*, 2014).

4 Finally, we evaluated the effect of HWTs on unrooted cuttings because olive
5 cultivars are mainly propagated by the nursery industry using this technique (Barranco
6 *et al.*, 2010). All of the temperature-exposure time combinations we tried were lethal
7 for the pathogen, however these combinations also severely affected the root
8 development of the cuttings. Unrooted cuttings have minimal lignification and are
9 more sensitive to heat treatment than the one-year old plants. Sanitation protocols for
10 soft olive cuttings thus require further optimization.

11 In summary, we have demonstrated that HATs (40 to 42°C for 6-12 h) can eliminate *V.*
12 *dahliae* infection in young olive plants. Similar to HWTs for grapevine (Waite &
13 Morton, 2007), these HATs have a number of advantages because their application is
14 simply based on the reliable monitoring of temperature, and are not time consuming
15 (6-12h or overnight). Even though some of these treatments might cause the death of
16 ~20% of the plants, their application to nursery mother plants is still economically
17 convenient. Mother plants will produce hundreds of cuttings and taking the risk of
18 spreading infected plants could be economically disastrous for the nurseries. These
19 HATs have also permitted the sanitisation of all valuable cultivars that are infected by
20 *V. dahliae* in the World Olive Germplasm Bank (WOGB) of Córdoba, such as Alfafara,
21 Buga, Caballo, Chorro, Cornezuelo de Jaén, Gordal de Granada, Habichuelero de
22 Grazalema, Macho de Jaén, Manzanilla de Almería, Mastoidis, Negrillo de Estepa,
23 Oblica, Picual de Almería, Racimal, Royal de Cazorla, Sabatera, Temprano, Uovo di
24 Piccione, Vallesa, Vaneta, and Varudo. Currently, every olive accession is propagated

1 using sterilised soil and systematically subjected to the optimised HATs prior to its
2 inclusion in the in the isolation repository of olive cultivars of the WOGB located at the
3 University of Córdoba. The hot air treatment developed is a useful tool for integrated
4 management of *Verticillium* wilt of olive.

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14

15 **FIGURE LEGENDS**

16 Figure 1. Effect of temperature (°C) and exposure time (minutes) on the mycelial
17 growth rate (mm/day) of defoliating (V-138 I and V-937 I) and non-defoliating (V-249 I
18 and V-789 I) *Verticillium dahliae* isolates from olive growing on potato dextrose agar.
19 The points represent the average of 10 Petri dishes. The bars represent the standard
20 error of each mean.

21 Figure 2. Effect of temperature (°C) and exposure time (hour) on the mycelial growth
22 rate (mm/day) of defoliating (V-138 I and V-117 I) and non-defoliating (V-249 I and V-
23 789 I) *Verticillium dahliae* isolates from olive growing on potato dextrose agar. The
24 points represent the average of 10 Petri dishes. The bars represent the standard error
25 of each mean.

26 Figure 3. Phenotypic expression of olive plants cvs. Picual (susceptible) and Frantoio
27 (resistant) that were infected by *Verticillium dahliae* two months after exposure to

1 moist hot air treatments (42 to 44°C for 12 h) with infected and non-treated control
2 plants.

3 Figure 4. Survival percentage of one-year-old plants of five olive cultivars that were
4 exposed to moist hot air treatments. The bars represent the average of six plants per
5 each treatment.

6 Figure 5. Relationship between the temperature (°C) and inhibition of growth per hour
7 of exposure (%/h) of five olive cultivars that were subjected to moist hot air
8 treatments.

9 Extra figure. Effect of temperature (°C) and exposure time (h) on the shoot growth
10 (mm) of plants of five olive cultivars after exposure to moist hot air treatment.

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1 TABLES

Table 1. Effect of temperature (°C) on the time [minutes (Experiment 1) or hours (Experiment 2)] required to cause 50 and 90% of mortality of isolates of *Verticillium dahliae* belonging to three Vegetative Compatibility Groups (VCG) and two pathotypes, defoliating (D) and non-defoliating (ND)

Experiment	Isolate	VCG (Pat)	Mortality (50% ^a)				Mortality (90%)			
			45°C ^b	47°C	50°C	55°C	45°C	47°C	50°C	55°C
1	V-789 I	4B (ND)	52.5	52.5a	47.5a	45.0a	58.5	58.5a	57.5a	57.0a
1	V-249 I	2A (ND)	52.5	52.5a	47.5a	45.0a	58.5	58.5a	57.5a	57.0a
1	V-937 I	1A (D)	>60.0	52.5a	45.0a	45.0a	>60.0	58.5a	57.0a	57.0a
1	V-138 I	1A (D)	>60.0	52.5a	47.5a	45.0a	>60.0	58.5a	57.5a	57.0a

Experiment	Isolate	VCG (Pat)	Mortality (50% ^a)				Mortality (90%)			
			40°C	42°C	44°C	46°C	40°C	42°C	44°C	46°C
2	V-789 I	4B (ND)	8.0a	8.0a	8.0a	6.0a	20.8a	20.8a	20.8a	19.2a
2	V-249 I	2A (ND)	8.0a	8.0a	6.0b	5.3a	20.8a	20.8a	19.2b	18.7a
2	V-138 I	1A (D)	7.3a	6.0b	6.0b	6.0a	20.3a	19.2b	19.2b	19.2a
2	V-117 I	1A (D)	8.0a	6.0b	6.0b	6.0a	20.8a	19.2b	19.2b	19.2a

^aKaplan–Meier percentiles.

^bFor each experiment and column, the groups with the same letter are not significantly different according to the Longrank test at $P = 0.05$.

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Table 2. Survival of olive plants (%) that were inoculated with *Verticillium dahliae* and subjected to moist hot air treatments (HATs)

Experiment /Cultivar	Treatment ^b	Survival plants after HATs (%) ^a	
		Infected Symptomless	Non-inoculated (Control)
Exp. 6 cv. Picual	40°C - 12 h	100	100
	42°C - 6 h	67	100
	42°C - 12 h	67	50
	44°C - 6 h	83	100
	44°C - 12 h	33	33
	46°C - 6 h	83	50
	46°C - 12 h	67	100
	Average	71	76
	Signification P ^c	0.620	
Exp. 7 cv. Frantoio	40°C - 6 h	100	100
	40°C - 12 h	67	100
	42°C - 6 h	83	100
	42°C - 12 h	83	100
	44°C - 6 h	83	100
	44°C - 12 h	67	100
	46°C - 6 h	67	100
	46°C - 12 h	33	100
	Average	73	100
	Signification P ^c	<0.001	

^aOlive potted plants were root-dip inoculated for 20 min in a suspension of 10^7 conidia ml^{-1} of *V. dahliae* defoliating pathotype

^bThe plants that were placed in closed plastic containers with 3 cm of water at the base, water sprayed, and incubated in darkened growth chambers at different temperatures and exposure times

^cSignificant differences between the inoculated and non-inoculated plants according to Chi-square test

Extra Table. Effect of cultivar (Cv.), temperature (T^a), exposure time (T^o) and experiment repetition (Rep) on olive plant survival after being subjected to Hot Air Treatments (HATs) according to Logistic Regression

Model Parameters	Deviance	Difference in Deviance	Degrees of Freedom ^a	P-value ^b
Rep., Cv., T^a , T^o , cte.	49.25			
Cv., T^a , T^o , cte.	49.41	0.16	1	0.689 (Rep)
Cv., T^a , cte.	114.97	65.56	2	< 0.001 (T^o)
Cv., T^o , cte.	95.72	46.31	2	< 0.001 (T^a)
Cv., T^a , T^o	157.00	107.59	2	< 0.001 (cte)
T^a , T^o , cte	57.69	8.28	2	< 0.0159 (cv.)

^aThe degrees of freedom were calculated as differences in the parameters with the most complete model

^bP-value according to the Chi-square test

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 4

Figure 5

Extra Figure